

ICCOB OA 001

**Protective effect of L-DOPA against Cypermethrin induced toxicity on reproductive
organs in female Japanese quail²**

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Cypermethrin (Cyp) is an insecticide which is used for the pest control all over world. It is also considered as one of the endocrine disruptors. It is considered as potent neurotoxic compounds associated with dopaminergic neurodegenerative activity. Present study was designed to test whether administration of L-dopa (a dopamine precursor) can protect toxic effect induced by Cyp on reproductive conditions in Japanese quail, *Coturnix coturnix japonica*. The adult female Japanese quail were divided into four groups (6 birds each). Group-1 received normal saline and served as control. Group-2 received Cyp (1mg/kg bw) dissolved in corn oil. Group-3 received L-dopa (5mg/100mg bw) and Group-4 received both Cyp and L-dopa. All treatments were given for 30 days. Results showed that treatment with Cyp caused significant decrease in follicle weight, size and number of follicles while L-dopa treated group showed significantly increased value was observed. Cyp + L-dopa treated group exhibited nearly normal appearance of the follicles weight and size when compared with control and other treated group while we observed decreased the number of follicles in comparison to control. It may be concluded that L-Dopa might be a potent protective agent against Cyp induced toxic effect on reproduction in Japanese quail.

Keywords: Cypermethrin (Cyp), Female Japanese quail, Follicle, L-dopa, Toxicity